

A Legal Vacuum Regarding the Procedural Rules for Expedited Proceedings in the Administrative Courts

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ABSTRACT: The status quo of fast-paced legal proceedings in the State Administrative Court has guaranteed legal certainty through Article 98 and Article 99 of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning the State Administrative Court; the Letter of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number 052/Td.TUN/III/1992 concerning operational guidelines formulated during training to improve judges' skills in TUN II courts in 1991; and Book II of the Technical Guidelines for Administration and Technical Affairs of the State Administrative Court. Based on the normative juridical research method, the researcher found that dispute resolution procedures are carried out differently. This is due to the absence of norms that specifically regulate deadlines for completion, trial agendas and document administration as an absolute prerequisite for resolving disputes with fast-paced procedures. Therefore, the researcher suggests that, if the parties want a fast resolution, there should be an agreement between the parties and the panel of judges that regular procedures will be used, but with acceleration to ensure that the principles of justice are not derogated. Additionally, the Supreme Court should formulate time limits and agendas to be included in the norms of fast-track procedures in the State Administrative Court.

KEYWORDS: Trial, Fast-Paced Procedure, State Administrative Court

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the mandate of Article 1, paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (UUD NRI 1945), Indonesia is a country based on law, which has legal consequences that can be seen and interpreted from various points of view. To understand this, Yusriadi divides legal science into three approaches, which ultimately lead to three schools of thought to legal science, which ultimately lead to three schools of thought in legal science¹. One of these schools of thought that has attracted the attention of researchers is the ideological approach, which views law as a collection of regulations containing noble fundamental principles that underpin the formation of law, such as justice, utility and balance.² Basically, laws and regulations are human masterpieces that have a specific purpose: to enforce order and regulate, maintain and direct society so that it always operates within a positive legal framework. This framework is based on the principle that wherever there is society, there is also a regulating law (*ubi societas, ibi ius*).

Implementing good governance in accordance with the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, and establishing the State Administrative Court, is further proof that Indonesia is a democratic, constitutional state where citizens' rights are protected. The State Administrative Court resolves state administrative disputes and organises government affairs at central and regional levels. Its function is to resolve disputes between the government and citizens, and to carry out judicial control of government actions deemed to violate administrative provisions (maladministration) or the law (abuse of power).³ From this provision, it can be seen that the State Administrative Court has a judicial function. This is emphasized in Article 47 of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts, which states that the court has the duty and authority to examine, decide, and resolve State Administrative disputes.

Like other branches of law, the State Administrative Court has its own characteristics with regard to procedural law. These are divided into four categories: ordinary, special, simple and expedited procedural law. Each type of procedural law has its own characteristics and procedures. The same applies to law enforcement in expedited procedural law. The term 'expedited procedural

¹ Yusriadi, Tebaran Pemikiran Kritis Hukum dan Masyarakat, (Surya Pena Gemilang: 2011), p.7.

² Ibid.

³ Anjas Yanasmoro Aji dan I Nengah Laba, "Kajian Hukum Sistem Pembuktian dalam Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara", Jurnal Lingkungan & Pembangunan, Vol. 2, No. 2, September 2018, p.28

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law' was first introduced in the Criminal Procedure Code, established in 1981.⁴ Five years later, the fast procedure was recognised and standardised in Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts. From the perspective of providing simple, fast and low-cost justice, the legal trial process involving fast procedures in the State Administrative Courts aims to reduce the court's backlog of cases while ensuring that the absolute prerequisites (*conditio sine qua non*) for a case to be eligible for fast procedural law are met. This involves assessing whether the plaintiff has experienced urgent interests as a result of the issuance of decisions and/or actions by state administrative agencies and/or officials.

In practice, examinations involving fast procedures are rarely carried out at the State Administrative Court. This was demonstrated during the researcher's study of the Semarang State Administrative Court, where examinations with fast procedures were last carried out in 2011. Legally, these examinations are regulated by Article 98(1) of Law No. 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts, and can be held if the plaintiff has a sufficiently urgent interest, as determined from the reasons given for requesting a fast procedure. The explanation of the aforementioned article also states that the plaintiff's interests are considered sufficiently urgent if they concern a state administrative decision, for example, the demolition of a building or house occupied by the plaintiff. The applicant's reasons can be used as criteria, provided they are acceptable. The accelerated process applies to both the examination and the decision.⁵

Based on the formulation of the explanation of norms *a quo* the author is interested in the phrase "not only the examination but also the decision is accelerated". This is because the fast procedure is only regulated through 2 (two) Articles, namely Article 98 and Article 99 of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts, where the author did not find further technical instructions on how the examination and decision process is accelerated, even in Article 99 paragraph (3) according to the researcher as a vague norm⁶ that does not provide further explanation regarding the time limit for answers and evidence for both parties, it is only stated "each is determined not to exceed 14 days".⁷

Such a status quo situation will certainly give rise to many legal interpretations by all State Administrative Court judges. The question is whether it is better to continue interpreting the law without formulating clear norms or to create legal rules that specifically regulate the examination procedures until the decision for cases that use fast procedures. Of course this provides more justice that prioritizes legal certainty for the justice seekers so that the principles of justice are not easily violated. This is in line with Gustav Radbruch's statement in his theory of 3 (three) basic legal values which explains that the creation of laws must be aimed at something that is beneficial or has legal benefits.⁸ The law, in essence, aims to produce pleasure or happiness for the masses.⁹ Based on this, the author will examine and analyze it further in an article entitled "**Legal Deficiencies in the Norms of Expedited Procedural Law in State Administrative Courts.**"

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The method employed in this study is the normative legal approach, which involves using legislation as the subject of analysis. The data collection technique utilised by the researcher in this study is a literature review, whereby data is obtained from academic writings and research published in articles and other journals. The approach used in this study is the normative legal approach. The legal approach in question views law as a norm or *das sollen*, as the discussion of issues in this study utilises legal materials.¹⁰

The approach used by the researcher in this study is a normative (doctrinal) juridical approach. The juridical approach is a method of analysis based on positive law, namely applicable laws and regulations (*ius constitutum*). Meanwhile, the¹¹ normative approach is an approach to several elements of legal norms such as basic norms, legal principles, court decisions, official decisions, and others as research objects.¹² The approach models used by the researcher are the statute approach, the case approach, and the conceptual approach. For research specifications, the analytical prescriptive specification is used, namely research that aims to

⁴Agung Pratama, "Pelaksanaan Acara Pemeriksaan Cepat dalam Perkara Pelanggaran Lalu Lintas di Pengadilan Negeri Palembang", Skripsi Fakultas Hukum Universitas Brawijaya, p.40.

⁵Vide Pasal 98 ayat (1) dan Penjelasannya Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 1986 tentang Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara.

⁶Sofwan, Haeruman and Rusnan, "Kejelasan Perumusan Norma dalam Pembentukan Undang-Undang (Kajian Terhadap Penggunaan Frasa Hukum dalam Perumusan Norma Undang-Undang)" *Jurnal Risalah Kenotariatan*, Vol. 2, No. 2, Desember 2021, p.32. An ambiguous norm is a lack of clarity in the formulated norm, so that an interpretation is required to resolve it.

⁷Vide Pasal 99 ayat 3 Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 1986 tentang Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara.

⁸M. Muslih, "*Negara Hukum Indonesia dalam Prespektif Teori Hukum Gustav Radbruch (Tiga Nilai Dasar Hukum)*", *Jurnal Legalitas*, Vol. IV, No. 1, Juni 2013, p.143.

⁹Endang Pratiwi, "Teori Utilitarianisme Jeremy Bentham: Tujuan Hukum atau Metode Pengujian Produk Hukum? Jeremy Bentham's Utilitarianism Theory: Legal Purpose or Methods of Legal Products Examination?", *Jurnal Konstitusi*, Vol. 19, No. 2, Juni 2022, p.273.

¹⁰Bambang Sugono, *Metode Penelitian Hukum*, (Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, 2006) pp.97- 98.

¹¹Roni Hanitjo Soemitro, *Metode Penelitian Hukum dan Jurimetri*, (Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia, 1982), p. 20.

¹²Muhaimin, *Metode Penelitian Hukum*, (Mataram: UPT. Mataram University Press, 2020), p.53.

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obtain suggestions or solutions regarding what should be done to overcome certain problems.¹³

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. The Trial Process with Fast Procedures in the State Administrative Court Based on Positive Law in Indonesia

The examination process with a fast procedure in the State Administrative Court in Indonesia is regulated in Article 98-99 of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning the State Administrative Court. According to Siti Soetami, the advantage of the examination process with a fast procedure is that the decision can be issued more quickly, but the disadvantage is that third parties cannot enter the trial process and the risk of obtaining legal facts is not as strong and convincing as in the regular procedure.¹⁴ Filing a lawsuit in the examination process with a fast procedure is the same as in the regular procedure, but the difference is that there are reasons outlined by the Plaintiff in his lawsuit letter explaining the urgency of the request to carry out a fast procedure.¹⁵ The filing of a lawsuit with a fast procedure must meet the following requirements:¹⁶

- a. The lawsuit must contain or state the reasons which form the basis for the Plaintiff to submit a request for the examination of the dispute to be expedited. The reasons which are prerequisites in Article 98 paragraph (1) of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts are mandatory conditions (*conditio sine qua non*).
- b. From the reasons put forward by the Plaintiff, it can be concluded that there must be a sufficiently urgent interest of the Plaintiff so that the settlement needs to be expedited. In this case, the provisions in Article 53 of Law Number 9 of 2004 concerning the First Amendment to Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts are applied but the meaning of the interest is expanded to include a sufficiently urgent interest.

Furthermore, after the application for examination by means of a fast procedure has been submitted and received by the Head of the State Administrative Court, within 14 (fourteen) days of receiving the application, the Head of the Court will issue a decision regarding whether the application will be granted or not granted.¹⁷ This provision means that the Chief Justice has the authority to grant or deny the *a quo* petition . In practice, the authority to issue a ruling on a request for expedited proceedings rests not only with the Chief Justice, but also with a judge appointed by the Chief Justice who can issue the ruling before the main case is examined.¹⁸ If the decision rejects the Plaintiff's application, there is no legal recourse against the decision.¹⁹ Conversely, if the decision grants the Plaintiff's application, the Chief Justice will appoint a single judge through his decision, as the expedited trial is conducted by a single judge.²⁰ Apart from appointing a judge, the Chief Justice also determines the place and time of the trial by his decision. All these determinations are made within a period of 7 (seven) days after the determination for an examination by express procedure is issued. Due to its expeditious nature the law also eliminates preparatory examinations.²¹ Then the deadline for the response and proof itself is set at a time not exceeding 14 (fourteen) days.²²

The provisions regarding the process of answering and providing evidence above actually give rise to two interpretations regarding the length of the examination process. First, if interpreted grammatically, the normative phrase is concluded that 14 (fourteen) days is a cumulative time for both the answer and the proof and if analyzed means 7 (seven) days for answering and providing evidence. Second, if interpreted extensively, the normative phrase then 14 (fourteen) days are for each stage. This means a grace period of 14 (fourteen) days for answering and providing evidence is also 14 (fourteen) days separately. So the cumulative process of answering and providing evidence is 28 (twenty-eight) days from the start of the first trial. Furthermore, Book II of the 2009 Technical Guidelines for Administrative and Technical State Administrative Courts provides a new legal principle that if the nature of the case being handled is very complex and the time limit for examination with fast procedures according to the provisions of the law is exceeded, then the examination will be carried out with ordinary procedures by means of a single judge returning it to the Chief Justice to be determined by the Panel of Judges who will examine the case. The Supreme Court also added that the element of urgent interest may also be possible for the Defendant so that the Defendant can also file a request. The difference in the status quo of the interpretation of examination with fast procedures that has been described above will be presented by the author in the table below:

First Interpretation	Information	Second Interpretation	Information
Lawsuit	: Granted for quick events	Lawsuit	: Granted for Quick event

¹³Soerjono Soekanto, *Pengantar Penelitian Hukum* (Jakarta: UI Press, 1986), p.15

¹⁴A. Siti Soetami, *Hukum Acara Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara*, (Bandung: Refika Aditama, 2007), edisi revisi, cetakan 5, p.89.

¹⁵R. Wiyono, *Hukum Acara Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara*, (Jakarta: Sinar Grafika, 2007), edisi 1, cetakan 1, pp.144 - 145.

¹⁶*Ibid.*

¹⁷Vide Pasal 98 ayat (2) Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 1986 tentang Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara.

¹⁸ Surat Mahkamah Agung Republik Indonesia Nomor 052/Td.TUN/III/1992 perihal juklak yang dirumuskan dalam pelatihan peningkatan keterampilan hakim peradilan TUN II tahun 1991, angka II.4.

¹⁹Vide Pasal 98 ayat (3) Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 1986 tentang Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara.

²⁰Vide Pasal 99 ayat (1) Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 1986 tentang Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara.

²¹Vide Pasal 99 ayat (2) Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 1986 tentang Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara.

²²Vide Pasal 99 ayat (3) Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 1986 tentang Peradilan Tata Usaha Negara.

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Determination of Grant	:	14 (fourteen) days	V E R S U S	Determination of Grant	:	14 (fourteen) days
Determination of trial date, appointment of sole judge	:	7 (seven) days		Determination of trial date, appointment of sole judge	:	7 (seven) days
Jinawab Answer Stage	:	7 (seven) days		Jinawab Answer Stages	:	14 (fourteen) days
Proof Stage	:	7 (seven) days		Proof Stage	:	14 (fourteen) days
Total Time	:	35 (thirty five) days		Total Time	:	49 (forty nine) days

From the table above, in addition to the length of time required for expedited proceedings in the State Administrative Court, the procedural stages of the trial agenda can be broadly interpreted. For regular proceedings, the proceedings begin with the reading of the lawsuit, the defendant's response, the rejoinder, the duplicate, the presentation of written evidence, witness testimony, expert testimony, the conclusion, and the verdict. Is the expedited proceedings similar to the examination under regular proceedings? Another interpretation concerns the limitations of the complexity of a case, which falls within the authority of a single judge to refer the case to the chief justice, who will then proceed with the examination under regular proceedings by the panel of judges. The parameters for assessing this will of course be left to the discretion of each panel of judges. The question is whether, if the time exceeds 35 (thirty- five) days or 49 (forty-nine) days, the case will continue with the examination under regular proceedings. The numerous interpretations of the expedited proceedings process require further study by the Supreme Court to find an ideal concept that aligns with current practice.

B. Legal Vacuum Due to the Ambivalence of the Fast-Procedural Trial Process in State Administrative Courts

The author will explain the legal interpretation of the legal vacuum in Articles 98-99, which regulate expedited proceedings, through several case studies, based on existing jurisprudence, as it has generated ambivalence and resulted in varying practices. The following is a description:

a. Decision of the Semarang State Administrative Court Number 54/G/2010/PTUN.SMG

- 1) The plaintiff filed the lawsuit on November 9, 2010
- 2) The Chief Justice of the State Administrative Court issued a ruling granting the Plaintiff's request to be examined by expedited proceedings on November 10, 2010.
- 3) The Determination of the Grant of a Quick Event is one with the Determination of Dismissal
- 4) The application with a fast procedure submitted by the Plaintiff is in accordance with Article 98 paragraph (1) of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts in conjunction with the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia's Letter of Attorney for Environmental Affairs of the PTUN Number: 052/Td.TUN/III/1992 Roman II Number 4 because the Plaintiff has outlined the reasons for the urgency and requested that the Head of the Semarang PTUN be examined with a fast procedure through his lawsuit letter.
- 5) That in order to test the urgent interests of the Plaintiff, we first examine the Plaintiff's reasons, where as described in the brief chronology above, in our opinion, if the Object of Dispute is examined using ordinary procedures, the settlement period can take months, especially since this case occurred in 2010 where Sema 2 of 2014 which limits the period for settling cases has not yet been issued, then in order to realize a fast settlement of the case in accordance with the principle of *litis finiri oportet* which upholds legal certainty for justice seekers, the Chief Justice is correct in granting the Plaintiff's request so that the losses suffered by the Plaintiff are not too large, especially after the issuance of the Object of Dispute is linked to the principle of *presumption iustae causa* , the Object of Dispute must be considered valid until the court declares otherwise. So it can be estimated that since the issuance of the Object of Dispute, the Plaintiff must comply with the contents of the Object of Dispute, namely closing his business until the court declares otherwise.
- 6) The researcher criticized the process of granting or not the request for a fast event by the Chief Justice where the time period was in accordance with the mandate of the Law, but for the product issued in the form of a Decision on Granting, it turned out that the product was combined with the Decision on Dismissal, even though if we compare the norms contained in Article 62 paragraph (1) vis a vis Article 98 of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts, grammatically there is a difference where the Dismissal Process is only to examine the formalities of the lawsuit including the authority of the court, Article 56, proper reasons, what is claimed is already in the KTUN and the premature or expired nature of a lawsuit. Meanwhile, in Article 98, more narrowly and specifically, it is only to examine whether the urgent interests or reasons stated by the Plaintiff in his lawsuit are worthy of being granted or not

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by the Chief Justice. Therefore, according to the author In fact, it is necessary to differentiate between the Dismissal Determination and the Determination of Granting or Not Granting the Examination with a Fast Procedure.

- 7) The examination process includes the reading of the lawsuit, the response, the presentation of evidence (witnesses and experts), and the conclusion. The details are as follows:
 - a) Defendant's Response November 23, 2010
 - b) Defendant's Response November 26, 2010
 - c) Evidence of Plaintiff and Defendant November 29, 2010
 - d) Additional Evidence and Witnesses from the Plaintiff and Defendant December 2, 2010
 - e) Additional Evidence and Witnesses from the Plaintiff and Defendant December 9, 2010
 - f) Conclusion December 13, 2010
 - g) Decision of December 20, 2010

The total time from the Determination of the Grant of the Fast Event to the Decision is approximately 29 (twenty nine) calendar days.

b. Decision of the Mataram State Administrative Court Number 2/G/2007/PTUN.MTR

- 1) The lawsuit was accepted and registered at the clerk's office of the Mataram State Administrative Court on January 10, 2007.
- 2) Determination of Granting of Fast-Procedure Procedure and Appointment of Single Judge January 12, 2007
- 3) Determination of trial day by single judge 15 January 2007
- 4) The Plaintiff's reasons in his application letter are in accordance with the arguments in the lawsuit, to prevent state losses and decisions issued by government agencies and/or officials have violated the law and general principles of good governance.
- 5) The examination process includes the reading of the lawsuit, the response, the presentation of evidence (witnesses and experts), and the conclusion. The details are as follows:
 - a) First hearing of the lawsuit reading January 15, 2007
 - b) Defendant's Response January 22, 2007
 - c) Reply January 24, 2007
 - d) Defendant's Duplicate and the Parties' Evidence January 29, 2007
 - e) Conclusion February 12, 2007
 - f) Decision of February 19, 2007

The total time from the Determination of the Grant of the Fast Event to the Decision is approximately 29 (twenty nine) calendar days.

c. Makassar State Administrative Court Decision Number 60/G/TF/2023/PTUN.MKS

- 1) The lawsuit was accepted and registered at the clerk's office of the Makassar State Administrative Court on July 28, 2023.
- 2) Determination of Dismissal by the Chief Justice July 31, 2023
- 3) Determination of Granting of Fast-Procedure Procedure and Appointment of Single Judge July 31, 2023
- 4) Dismissal Determination and Quick Event Determination products are separated
- 5) Determination of the Trial Date by the Single Judge is July 31, 2023
- 6) The process of examining the lawsuit includes reading the complaint, answering the case, presenting evidence, and concluding the case. The details are as follows:
 - a) Lawsuit Reading August 7, 2023
 - b) Defendant's Response August 14, 2023
 - c) Defendant's Response August 16, 2023
 - d) Evidence of the Parties August 22, 2023
 - e) Additional Evidence of the Parties August 29, 2023
 - f) Conclusion of the Parties September 5, 2023
 - g) Reading of the Verdict September 8, 2023

The total time from the Determination of the Grant of the Fast Event to the Decision is approximately 30 (thirty) calendar days.

Based on the 3 (three) samples of jurisprudence above, it can be concluded that First, the average length of time for completing an examination with a fast procedure is 30 (thirty) calendar days (according to the first interpretation, no more than 35 (thirty- five) days). Then, for the stages of the proceedings, some provide the opportunity to submit a reply and duplicate (Mataram Administrative Court) and 2 (two) others do not have a reply or duplicate. Lastly, for the product of the determination of granting a fast event, the Semarang PTUN combines it with the Dismissal Determination, while the Makassar PTUN separates the two (two) determinations. The portrait of the differences in the three legal interpretation practices in organizing trials with fast procedures is

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a result of the legal vacuum of normative trials with fast procedures in Articles 98-99 of Law Number 5 of 1986. The law must actually have clarity because the clearer the norm, the higher the legal certainty. For this reason, in the future, an update is needed, either by creating new legal rules through the formulation of the Supreme Court chamber or issuing technical instructions through a letter from the Chief Justice of the Supreme Court for the sake of uniformity in the process of examining cases with fast procedures in the State Administrative Court environment.

CONCLUSIONS

Legally, the process of examining fast proceedings in the State Administrative Court is currently still guided by the provisions of Article 98-99 of Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts in conjunction with the Letter of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number 052/Td.TUN/III/1992 concerning the operational guidelines formulated in the training to improve the skills of judges in the TUN II court in 1991, number II.4. in conjunction with Book II of the Technical Guidelines for Administration and Technical Procedures for State Administrative Courts where researchers conclude that the status quo of the current normative arrangements is experiencing a legal vacuum where many legal interpretations will occur to organize the trial process with fast proceedings. The legal vacuum must be filled through the formation of new norms that can be stated in the form of revising Law Number 5 of 1986 concerning State Administrative Courts, especially regarding the text of Articles 98-99. In addition, the Supreme Court is expected to issue technical instructions or guidelines for resolving disputes examined with fast proceedings to overcome the temporary legal norm vacuum.

In practice, the legal vacuum a quo results in differences in the process of resolving cases using expedited proceedings. First, the timeframe, according to the first interpretation, does not exceed 35 (thirty- five) days. Second, some stages of the examination process include a duplicate reply, while others do not. Third, some dismissal decisions are combined with the decision to grant expedited proceedings, while others are separated. These differences in practice can actually be resolved by mutual agreement or consent from the parties. If the nature of the dispute is complex and the parties desire a speedy resolution, then expedited proceedings are not necessary, but rather regular proceedings, with expedited procedures that maintain the principles of justice.

RECOMMENDATION

BPJS should provide a high coverage limit for its members' health insurance so that they can access advanced medical equipment using their BPJS membership contributions

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